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Context:

A robotic fish accepted by animals as conspecifics is a very powerful tool in behavioral biology. To obtain the acceptance of the device towards the animals, it should generate some visual stimuli that can be perceived by a living fish as attractive signals. In this work, we introduce a novel design of a robotic fish lure based on a Rigid-Flex Printed Circuit Board (PCB) for experiments on the fish collective behavior.

The external shape of the lure was defined using the 3D scan of a dead zebrafish *Danio Rerio* (Fig. 4). The zebrafish was scanned using a Stereoscan 3D Breuckmann Stereo SCAN 3D with two cameras of 1.4 megapixels. The surfaces retrieved by the scanner were processed and scaled in order to design a mold with the desired undercut of the zebrafish

Rigid-Flex PCB is the name given to a PCB that is a combination of both flexible and rigid circuits. Rigid-Flex PCBs give thus the ability to design the circuitry to fit a three-dimensional device in a more optimal way. The Figure below shows the design of the Rigid-Flex PCB made for this study. It is composed of 4 parts that are separated by flexible joints that only contains circuit tracks.

We used a miniature Lithium Polymer battery bought from SparkFun that can be recharged through the eyes of the fish that are made of brass. We selected a micro step gear motor MF03G of Seiko Precision Inc. for the actuation of the caudal peduncle.

The mechanical design of the lure was made using PTC CREO Parametric, educational edition. a) Eyes. b) IR sensor. c) Contacts to reprogram the device. d) Anal fin. e) Stepper motor. f) Dorsal fin. g) Caudal peduncle. h) Caudal fin.

We performed a successful remote controlled experiment with the lure below 30 cm water layer. The waterproofness of the lure was validated. The actuated tail was found to run well, with amplitudes measured between 0 and 23 degrees and frequencies between 0 and 20 Hz.

Results:

We showed that when using Rigid-Flex PCB techniques, we could overcome the miniaturization of a miniature robotic device while adding PCB surface to mount electronic components.

We also showed that the lure designed in this study is almost half the length of the lure presented in other related studies.

Version	Old	New
Max. length [mm]	80	63
Max. width [mm]	10	11
Max. height [mm]	20	14
PCB surface [mm ²]	858	1002
Estimated volume [mm ³]	8320	5390
Mass [g]	10.48	5.9

Future Works:

In further work, we will use this design coupled with an external wheeled mobile robot to allow steering from below the tank in order to perform interaction experiments with living zebrafish *Danio Rerio*.

Acknowledgements:

This work was supported by the EU-ICT project ASSISlbf, No. 601074.

